

the treatment, Leb Mue Nahng 111, Kurkaruppan, Nam Sagui 19, and FR13A had the highest dry weight and highest leaf area per plant. Based on dry matter produced, those four varieties should perform well in the shade. FR13A and Kurkaruppan also show the least reduction in plant weight at higher degrees of shading.

A set of plants was placed in total darkness for 7 d to test if this could be a faster way of screening for shade tolerance. Generally, the varieties with high dry matter weight at 55% shading had high survival rate in complete darkness ($r = 0.578^*$). The correlation, however is not very high and screening at 55% shading would be a better method.

Thin leaves or low specific leaf

Effect of shade on rice seedlings.^a

Variety	Dry matter (mg/plant) at 55% shade	Decrease (%) in dry matter at 55% shade	Leaf area (cm ²) /plant at 55% shade	SLW ^b (mg/dm ²) in normal light	Survival (%) at 7 d darkness				
IR1529-680-3-2	125	ef	56 a	28.75	g	3.27 a	37	bcd	
IR52	156	de	39 b	39.42	ef	2.10	de	83 a	
RD19	180	cd	52 ab	44.02	de	1.97	e	93 a	
Thavalu (acc. 15314)	176	cd	54 a	34.70	f	2.91	b	70 abc	
Leb Mue Nahng 111	213	bc	58 a	48.73	cd	2.55	c	63 abc	
Kurkaruppan	233	ab	58 a	57.87	b	2.52	c	83 ab	
Nam Sagui	226	ab	55 a	54.30	bc	2.31	cde	40 bcd	
FR13A	263	a	42 ab	68.00	a	2.27	cde	73 abc	
IR42	104	f	50 ab	27.07	gh	2.37	cd	27	cd
IR20	91	f	57 a	21.67	h	2.33	cde	30	cd

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Specific leaf weight.

weight (SLW), said to be characteristic of varieties suitable for low light intensities, is found in FR13A, IR52, and RD19. Growing the varieties to maturity

to obtain grain yield would give the ultimate measure of their shade tolerance. Further studies, using more varieties, need to be made. □

Cropping systems

Potential of rice-based multiple cropping sequences for irrigated conditions in Uttar Pradesh

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Rice is the predominant crop in most medium-altitude irrigated valleys in the UP hills. The most popular crop rotations are rice (Jun-Oct) – wheat (Nov-May) and rice (Jul-Oct) – potato (Feb-Jun), with an intervening fallow period from late Oct to mid-Feb. Cropping intensity is restricted to 200%.

We conducted a fixed plot field study from 1978 to 1981 at the VPKAS experimental farms, Hawalbagh, to determine ways of increasing cropping intensity. Four crop sequences with 34 crops/year were compared with the popular 2 crop rice – wheat rotation. Data for the rice – potato rotation were also compiled.

Short-duration varieties were used in the intensive cropping sequences and medium-duration varieties were planted in the less intensive sequences. Recommended cultural practices were adopted

Yield, costs, and returns in 1978–81 for irrigated rice-based cropping systems in UP, India.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice (VL Dhan 8) - wheat (VL Gehun 421)	4.7 4.9	497	630	2.4
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - rapeseed (T9) - potato (K. Jeoti)	5.1 1.2 23.0	988	1,019	2.1
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - cabbage (Golden acre) - maize for green cobs (VL Makka 16)	3.9 37.4 62,666 ^a	940	1,485	2.6
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - radish (Japanese white long) - pea (vegetable pod Arkel) - French bean (vegetable pod) VL Bauni 1	3.7 30.4 13.3 9.3	854	1,456	2.7

^a Number of cobs.

for all crops.

Highest average annual net returns were from a rice – cabbage – maize (green cobs) rotation followed by rice – radish – pea (vegetable) – French bean (vegetable) and rice – rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*) – potato sequences. Rice – wheat yielded the lowest net return (see table).

From the benefit-cost ratio point of view, the rice – radish – pea (vegetable)

– French bean (vegetable) sequence was best, followed by rice – cabbage – maize (green cobs). However, these sequences can be adopted only near marketplaces because vegetables are an important component. In places away from marketing centers, rice – rapeseed – potato can be adopted to increase profits. This pattern is being adopted by some cultivators. □